

Received: 11 Dec 2020/ Accepted: 16 Mar 2021/ Published: 31 May 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4876610>

Biofiber derived from Aquatic Plants and Weeds which is a menace otherwise for Eco-friendly value-added products with Biopolymers

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This work was presented at the International Conference on Natural Polymers (ICNP-2019) held during 6-8, December 2019 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam, Kerala, India.

Introduction: Water hyacinth is one possible source of natural fiber which is low cost, non-toxic, and abundant in Indonesia. It has approximately 40% cellulose content which is comparable with the fiber content from other sources (1). Cellulose content has an important influence on the properties of biocomposites. In previous studies the higher cellulose content leads to better mechanical and thermal properties reported (2,3,4). Current work proposes the use of water hyacinth effectively in various products effectively in various natural rubber based composites/products. The dried mass was characterized with respect to the particle size and DSC was used to determine the thermal characteristics. Dried and powdered mass was used in natural rubber by casting and molding of the products so that it can be used for various applications. Various physical and mechanical properties of products including tensile strength were studied. The major highlight of the products is its biodegradability as it is made of completely biodegradable materials.

Methods: Natural rubber (NR), ISNR 5 from local suppliers and toluene as solvent were used were laboratory grade. Water hyacinth used for this study was collected from the local ponds. Plants collected were washed thoroughly several times and chopped into small pieces. It was then dried and milled with grinder to obtain smaller pieces. The powdered water hyacinth was sieved to obtain different particle size powder and were sorted into four groups (grades 1 to 4) as per the sieved sizes. The bulk densities for the powdered sample were determined. The powdered samples were sealed and stored at room temperature (RT) until used. The product preparation was done by two methods, natural rubber solution was prepared and mixed the powder into it, then casted on glass plates to remove solvents. Another method was using two roll mill dry rubber was mixed with powder and molded in compression molding machine.

Results & Discussions: Bulk density of the powder increases with decrease in particle size of the powder. It is because of more free space available between the fibers and less close packing. DSC curve of water hyacinth shows endothermic peak which is corresponding melting. TGA was taken for water hyacinth fiber, in which the initial weight loss was at around 100°C and can be attributed to removal of entrapped water and further weight loss at 150°C. Smaller particles bind with natural rubber, the % of water absorption was decreased. When the amount of rubber increases, higher resistance towards the alkali was observed. It is found that the tensile strength gradually decreased when the particle size increased. Acid resistance not only depends upon the amount of rubber used but also it depends on the particle size. The reason for reduction of tensile strength is due to the poor adhesion between powder particle and rubber. The flexibility of the rubber get changes as powders are added, it is found that medium size particles gave highest as there is improved flexibility for the compounds. It is very clear that as the particle size increases the modulus increases which is contributed by the fibrous fillers. The filler loading upto 30 % loading were showing increasing modulus and then showing decreasing tendency.

Conclusions: This project explored the possibility of using water hyacinth powder as filler in natural rubber. Effect of the amount of filler on natural rubber were investigated. It was found that, when smaller amount of water hyacinth powder large amount of filler can be added and better quality sheets were obtained. The smallest particle size fillers can be loaded upto 30 % successfully into the natural rubber matrices and found improving the modulus.

Key words: Aquatic Plants, Biopolymers, Water hyacinth

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